

An Explainable AI (XAI) Approach to the Scale-up of Artificial Intelligence Startups

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Abstract

Drawing on multi-source quantitative data for 357 Korean AI startups (2020–2022), this study exploratorily characterizes the relative importance and the nonlinear trajectory shapes of financial resource signals versus non-financial certification signals in predicting revenue scale-up. Five algorithms drawn from three model families — benchmark, tree-based ensembles, and deep learning (Logistic Regression, Random Forest, XGBoost, CatBoost, ANN) — are evaluated under nested cross-validation. Random Forest is selected as the champion model because it simultaneously satisfies three criteria: predictive performance (CV AUROC), interpretive stability appropriate for PDP, and a generalization gap of +0.077. On the champion model we conduct global feature-importance analysis (Gini-based and permutation importance combined) and Partial Dependence Plot (PDP) analysis. Two principal findings emerge. First, the importance of non-financial certification signals is comparable to or marginally exceeds that of financial resource signals, producing a reversal vis-à-vis the linear correlation results. Second, the trajectory shapes differ across signal types: VC investment exhibits a clearly stepwise inflection, whereas the non-financial certification signals show only modest variation in predicted probability. Methodologically, the paper contributes (i) a pre-analysis sensitivity check that diagnoses a double-correction problem in class-imbalance handling, (ii) a diagnostic interpretation of class overlap, and (iii) an exploratory XAI framework. Reference-grade implications for founders, venture investors, and policymakers are offered.

Keywords: *AI startups; revenue scale-up; signaling theory; non-financial certification signals; machine learning; explainable AI (XAI); partial dependence plot (PDP); exploratory analysis.*

I. Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is acting as a general-purpose technology that drives innovation and productivity across virtually every industry. In the process of converting this transformative potential into realized productivity gains, the complementary innovation capacity of startups plays a pivotal mediating role (Brynjolfsson et al., 2018; Cockburn et al., 2018). AI ventures have therefore emerged as core actors of the innovation ecosystem (Chalmers et al., 2021; Obschonka & Audretsch, 2020), and major economies treat the cultivation of AI startup ecosystems as a strategic agenda for national competitiveness (Stanford HAI, 2025).

According to the AI Index 2025 (Stanford HAI, 2025), Korea's private AI investment in 2024 amounted to USD 1.33 billion — a year-on-year decline. Cumulative investment over the past decade is roughly 1/50 that of the United States and 1/6 that of China. Domestic AI venture investment grew 75.1% year-on-year to KRW 969.4 billion in 2024 (MSS, 2024), yet Korean firms remain marginal in the global AI frontier. This pattern suggests that quantitative capital expansion does not translate directly into scale-up or global competitiveness. What determines the growth of Korean AI startups appears to lie not merely in technology development or fundraising, but in how external resources and signals accumulate and flow into firm-level performance.

The literature on the growth of early-stage deep-tech ventures has analyzed, primarily through the lens of signaling theory (Spence, 1973), how external certification indicators — VC investment, intellectual property, public support, awards — function as proxies for firm quality under severe information asymmetry (Connelly et al., 2011; Colombo, 2021; Bafera & Kleinert, 2023). Plummer et al. (2016) showed that combinations of signals exert stronger validation than single signals, and Zimmerman and Zeitz (2002) argued that ventures must cross a Threshold of Legitimacy convincing market participants of their viability in order to acquire sustainable growth resources.

Existing work, however, has tended to treat the cumulative effect of signals as a homogeneous mechanism, implicitly assuming that financial signals (e.g., VC investment) and non-financial certification signals (e.g., government support, awards, IP) all contribute to growth through the same nonlinear trajectory. The two types differ fundamentally in their verification path and information transmission. Financial signals are broad third-party signals carrying professional due diligence and capital infusion, transmitted as discrete events at each round (Bafera & Kleinert, 2023; Davila et al., 2003). Non-financial certification signals tend to build legitimacy gradually through repeated renewal and accumulation. Howell (2017) reports that the signaling effect of government grants is strong at the early stage but attenuates later, and Islam et al. (2018) document gradual decay in the post-award signal. Despite these structural differences, no prior empirical study has data-drivenly compared whether the two signal types

unfold along distinct nonlinear trajectories during scale-up.

The bulk of prior empirical work has relied on traditional linear methods such as OLS regression or panel fixed-effects models. These models presuppose proportional marginal effects across the variable's range and are structurally limited in distinguishing different nonlinear patterns of signal accumulation. The average R^2 of econometric growth models is below 10% (Coad, 2009), and the entrepreneurship ecosystem itself behaves as a highly nonlinear complex system (Crawford et al., 2015; Stam, 2015). Recent startup research has therefore introduced tree-based ensembles and explainable AI (XAI) (Żbikowski & Antosiuk, 2021; Shi et al., 2024; Bidgoli et al., 2024). Yet these studies remain anchored in SHAP-based feature-importance rankings and do not characterize the trajectory along which a particular signal's accumulation reshapes the growth probability (Cook et al., 2021). More fundamentally, prior XAI work treats signal variables as a homogeneous set, excluding the very possibility that financial and non-financial signals exhibit distinct nonlinear patterns. The Korean entrepreneurship ecosystem has its own structural particularity: state-led R&D and entrepreneurship support policies (e.g., TIPS) act as a powerful primer for the venture capital market (KISTEP, 2023; Kim et al., 2024). In such an environment, government program awards and public-sector recognition plausibly function as signal capital that pulls in subsequent private investment. A systematic empirical examination of how each signal type contributes to scale-up in this Korean context, however, has yet to be conducted.

To address these theoretical and methodological gaps, this study aims to data-drivenly identify whether external signal variables follow differentiated nonlinear trajectories in scale-up depending on their type, in the heavily information-asymmetric Korean AI entrepreneurship ecosystem. Specifically, it asks whether financial signals (VC investment) and non-financial certification signals (government program participation, awards, IP) manifest distinct nonlinear patterns — for instance, a single threshold effect at a particular cumulative point versus a smooth gradual accumulation effect. To this end, tree-based ensembles (Random Forest, XGBoost, CatBoost) and an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) compete with a logistic regression benchmark, and a Partial Dependence Plot (PDP)-based XAI framework (Friedman, 2001) is applied to track each signal's marginal-effect trajectory at a macro level. Within a predictive framework that doubly controls for overfitting and methodological bias through nested cross-validation and pre-treatment sensitivity analysis, we pose three research questions:

- RQ1. In predicting the scale-up of early AI startups, do nonlinear models offer a meaningful predictive advantage over traditional linear models?
- RQ2. Under XAI-based global feature-importance analysis, what is the relative importance of financial signals versus non-financial certification signals, and how does it differ from the significance pattern produced by traditional linear models?

- **RQ3. In PDP analysis, what nonlinear trajectory shapes do financial signals (VC investment) and non-financial certification signals (government programs, awards, IP) trace, and are there observable structural differences between the two types? How can the discovered patterns be interpreted from the standpoint of signaling theory?**

This study contributes along three dimensions. Theoretically, it brings the cumulative-effect discussion of signaling theory into a typology of trajectory shapes by signal type. Whereas prior work treats financial and non-financial signals as a homogeneous set, we directly compare their trajectory shapes within a single analytic frame and connect the observed patterns post hoc to the signal-classification axes of Bafera and Kleinert (2023) and the legitimacy threshold of Zimmerman and Zeitz (2002). Methodologically, by moving beyond SHAP-style micro-decomposition and visualizing the continuous marginal-effect trajectory of each predictor with PDP, we offer a transparent global interpretation framework. We further institutionalize methodological transparency through a sensitivity check across class-imbalance treatments and through nested cross-validation, providing a methodological reference point for XAI-based startup research in small-sample settings. Practically, we offer an empirical basis on which differentiated screening and policy-design schemes can be built for each signal type.

The remainder of this paper proceeds as follows. Section II reviews the deep-tech entrepreneurship ecosystem, signaling theory and signal-type heterogeneity, and the ML/XAI methodology. Section III describes the data and the predictive model design. Section IV presents the empirical results and discussion. Section V concludes.

II. Theoretical Background and Prior Research

2.1 Deep-Tech Entrepreneurship and the Structural Features of Scale-up

Deep-tech ventures are rooted in disruptive science-based technology and are intrinsically distinct from typical digital-solution startups, which iterate quickly under a Lean approach (Kask & Linton, 2023; Dionisio et al., 2023). The AI industry, in particular, is characterized by high technological intensity, large up-front costs for compute and data, and a rapid pace of technological evolution (Cockburn et al., 2018), which inevitably entails sizeable initial capital requirements and a long time-to-market (Romme et al., 2023). This risk structure produces a deeper and more persistent funding gap — the Valley of Death — between invention and innovation than is observed for ordinary IT startups (Auerswald & Branscomb, 2003).

The Valley of Death originates fundamentally from extreme information asymmetry between founders and investors. Venture capital and other external investors, lacking specialized scientific knowledge in frontier technologies, are exposed to adverse-selection risk; this neutralizes traditional financial valuation and suppresses early private investment, producing

inefficiencies in the venture capital market (Welter & Holcomb, 2023). For deep-tech ventures to cross the Valley of Death and enter a sustained growth trajectory, internal capability is insufficient; strategic dependence on external ecosystem resources becomes unavoidable.

Within the entrepreneurship ecosystem, scale-up is regarded as a key driver not only of firm survival but of national productivity and innovation (OECD, 2021). The traditional High-Growth Enterprise (HGE) definition — at least 10 employees at the start of observation and three consecutive years of average annual employment or revenue growth above 20% (Eurostat-OECD, 2007) — has been criticized for omitting the genuine job-creation effects of early-surviving firms (Daunfeldt et al., 2015). Recent organization-development work redefines scale-up as a dynamic developmental stage in which internal resources and capabilities are fundamentally reconfigured (Monteiro, 2019; Mula et al., 2024). Coviello et al. (2024) draw a careful distinction among Scaling, Scalability, and Scale-up, and recommend that scale-up be understood as an organizational structural transition into a stable growth trajectory.

Achieving scale-up in deep-tech is characterized by high dependence on external ecosystem resources. Dionisio et al. (2023) empirically show that deep-tech entrepreneurial success requires the combination of individual technological capability with the political and business environment, the national R&D infrastructure, and absorptive capacity. Knowledge transfer from universities and research institutes (Heaton et al., 2019; O'Reilly et al., 2019), strategic partnerships with supply-chain and regulatory actors (Mohr et al., 2014), and venture-capital funding combined with value-added effects (Bertoni et al., 2011; Bock et al., 2018) are confirmed as essential conditions for meaningful growth. Stuart (2000) shows that interfirm cooperation in high-tech industries positively affects revenue growth, and Teece (2007) argues that the dynamic capabilities required to integrate and reconfigure such external resources determine sustained competitive advantage. These arguments imply that deep-tech ventures must strategically transmit objective signals demonstrating their technological potential and organizational legitimacy in order to obtain specialized external capital and ecosystem resources.

2.2 Signaling Theory and Its Extension to Entrepreneurial Finance

Although the resource-based view (RBV) emphasizes internal resources and technological capabilities as the source of competitive advantage (Barney, 1991), it is limited as a mechanism for resolving the severe information asymmetry of early deep-tech ecosystems. Signaling theory (Spence, 1973) complements RBV: in markets where quality is unobservable, high-quality actors send observable proxies that low-quality actors cannot easily mimic, thereby resolving information asymmetry.

In management and venture finance, signaling has become a core analytic frame for understanding how new ventures acquire external resources (Connelly et al., 2011; Colombo,

2021; Bafera & Kleinert, 2023). Shane and Stuart (2002) document the role of direct and indirect founder–investor social ties as decisive determinants of venture performance, illuminating the brokering function of networks. External certification signals — IP, government R&D awards, prizes — function repeatedly as proxies for firm quality where outsiders cannot fully assess internal technical capability (Ahlers et al., 2015; Hsu & Ziedonis, 2013; Conti et al., 2013). Because no single signal commands market trust under deep uncertainty, Plummer et al. (2016) demonstrate that combinations of signals deliver substantially stronger validation than individual signals for raising early external capital. Courtney et al. (2017) further show that endorsement by governments or credible third parties reduces information asymmetry more effectively than self-claims, and Colombo et al. (2019) find that structural-capital signals such as patents interact with human-capital signals to enhance early-stage funding probability.

Theoretically extending these cumulative and combinatorial effects, Zimmerman and Zeitz (2002) argue that to obtain growth resources, a new venture must pass a threshold of legitimacy beyond which it is recognized as a credible market actor; legitimacy is itself an antecedent resource that enables further resource acquisition. Growth trajectories before and after this threshold are qualitatively distinct (Rutherford & Buller, 2007), and ventures face multiple thresholds as they migrate from initial survival into scale-up (Fisher et al., 2016). These arguments suggest that the accumulation of external signals does not contribute to growth proportionally; instead, it may switch nonlinearly once a certain accumulation level is reached.

2.3 Heterogeneity of Signal Types: Breadth, Sender, and Verification Mode

The signaling literature has nonetheless tended to assume a homogeneous mechanism for cumulative effects — i.e., that VC investment and non-financial certification signals (government support, awards, IP) all contribute to growth through the same nonlinear trajectory. Recent systematic reviews argue that this homogeneity assumption has constrained the explanatory power of the theory and call for finer typing of signals (Connelly et al., 2011; Colombo, 2021; Bafera & Kleinert, 2023). Bafera and Kleinert (2023) propose three constituent axes: message breadth (broad vs. narrow), sender (internal vs. third-party), and verification mode (discrete verification vs. cumulative reputation).

VC investment is presented as a prototypical broad signal, since professional investors evaluate multiple quality dimensions during due diligence. Patents, by contrast, sit closer to a narrow signal restricted to a single technological dimension (Hoenig & Henkel, 2015), while government program selection and awards transmit information whose breadth depends on the screening body's evaluative criteria. Internal signals are sent by the founder or the firm itself; third-party signals are issued when independent external actors certify the firm. Third-party signals tend to be more credible because the sender is exposed to penalty cost (reputation

damage). VC investment is a third-party signal because professional investors stake capital while signaling, and government R&D support is a third-party signal mediated by public agencies. Patents are at the boundary, since they are filed and registered by the firm but examined by a patent office. The third axis — discrete versus cumulative verification — has not been theorized explicitly in the prior literature, but recent empirical work increasingly suggests that signal types may differ qualitatively in their verification mode.

2.4 Theoretical Heterogeneity between Financial and Non-Financial Certification Signals

The three axes above suggest that financial signals (VC investment) and non-financial certification signals (government support, awards, IP) may exhibit distinct properties along three dimensions. First, on message breadth: each VC investment round can be read as a broad signal of multidimensional quality, since due diligence integrates assessment across team, market, technology, and financials (Bafera & Kleinert, 2023; Davila et al., 2003). Patents are closer to narrow signals (Hoenig & Henkel, 2015), and government program awards or prizes have an information span more limited than that of VC due diligence.

Second, on sender and signal cost: VC investors are third-party senders exposed to dual risks — capital and reputational — which heightens signal credibility (Bafera & Kleinert, 2023). Public agencies that award R&D grants likewise act as third-party certifiers via screening; yet their evaluative criteria, time horizons, and capital exposure differ from those of VCs. Patents straddle the internal/third-party boundary.

Third, on verification mode and temporal dynamics: prior empirical work indicates that the effect of non-financial certification signals can change in complex ways across time and cumulative count. Howell (2017) finds that SBIR Phase 1 grants strongly affect VC funding and patenting in the U.S., whereas Phase 2's incremental effect is more limited, and Islam et al. (2018) document a dynamic post-award pattern. These findings suggest that the effect of non-financial certification signals is unlikely to be a simple linear accumulation. For VC investment, Mohammadi et al. (2014) show that the participation of incumbent investors in follow-on rounds acts as an important re-validation signal to subsequent investors, raising the possibility that the accumulation of investment rounds carries meaning beyond simple summation.

Despite these theoretical distinctions and individual findings, whether financial and non-financial certification signals exhibit specific nonlinear patterns along scale-up trajectories — and whether observable structural differences exist between the two types — remains an open question that has not been examined systematically. Existing XAI-based startup studies have likewise treated signal variables as a homogeneous set focused on importance rankings (Bidgoli et al., 2024; Żbikowski & Antosiuk, 2021). The present study addresses this gap not through ex-

ante hypothesis testing but through PDP-based exploratory analysis, with theoretical implications discussed post hoc.

2.5 Empirical Studies of Strategic Determinants of Scale-up in Tech Ventures

Building on signaling theory and organizational legitimacy, empirical work has accumulated on the strategic determinants of early tech-venture scale-up. We review prior studies in three categories — financial signals (VC), public certification signals (government support), and technology/reputation signals (IP, awards) — and identify the methodological limitations that motivate our approach.

In tech-venture ecosystems VCs are not just suppliers of capital but financial-signal senders that transmit invested-firm potential to the market. Davila et al. (2003) show that VC-backed startups achieve significantly higher employment and revenue growth, demonstrating a certification effect of early financial investment on subsequent growth. Bertoni et al. (2011) and Bock et al. (2018) report that VCs drive growth not only through capital provision but through value-added activities and coaching, so that VC investment operates simultaneously through a signaling channel and a resource channel.

VCs are known to combine quantitative and qualitative external certification indicators alongside team capability when screening startups (Gompers et al., 2020). This integrated assessment implies that each investment round functions as a verification event involving multidimensional screening. Mohammadi et al. (2014) further suggest that incumbent participation in follow-on rounds acts as a re-validation signal to subsequent investors, so that the relationship between rounds carries meaning beyond simple accumulation. That said, deep-tech ventures need prior signals to attest to technical feasibility and survival before raising initial VC; VC investment is therefore better understood as the result of accumulated prior signal capital than as a starting point of growth (Islam et al., 2018), implying that the effect of VC must be analyzed jointly with non-financial signals.

Government-led entrepreneurship support and R&D grants — designed to compensate for early-stage capital-market failures — are central conduits of ex-ante signals. Howell (2017) finds that U.S. SBIR Phase 1 grants positively affect subsequent VC funding and patenting, while Phase 2 grants from the same program have more limited incremental effects. Islam et al. (2018) confirm that government grants raise the probability of subsequent VC funding while the effect itself shifts dynamically over time. These findings suggest that the effect of public support signals is neither linear nor monotone but has a temporal and stage-dependent structure. Söderblom et al. (2015) frame this as output additionality: government support fosters firm growth not so much through immediate financial returns as through the mediating accumulation of resources and the attraction of follow-on signals.

In Korea — where state-led entrepreneurship policy is especially active — public R&D and venture support (e.g., TIPS) act as a primer for the venture capital market (KISTEP, 2023; Kim et al., 2024). Government support functions as a moderator of the relationship between firms' knowledge capability and revenue (Choi et al., 2021), and government program awards and recognitions are plausibly important certification signals for follow-on private investment. Korean studies further document the complexity of public-support effects: Ryu and Ahn (2022) find a delayed pattern in which R&D subsidies' effect is initially negative and turns positive over time, and Kim and Yu (2021) attempted to verify nonlinearity but were unable to recover specific thresholds or saturation points within a traditional statistical framework. These findings suggest that public-support signals cannot be adequately captured by simple linear specifications, but the concrete shape of the relationship has not been characterized.

On technology/reputation signals: Hsu and Ziedonis (2013) show that patents serve both as instruments of technological protection and as signals of technological quality for investors, positively affecting early valuations. Conti et al. (2013) confirm that early-stage investors use the founder's patent holdings and external competition awards as reputation indicators in their decisions. Hoenig and Henkel (2015) find that VCs assign higher value to research alliances than to patents, indicating that the value of patent signals is confined to a relatively narrow technical dimension. These studies confirm that technology/reputation signals contribute to quality assessment, but they leave unspecified the functional shape through which the contribution translates into growth.

Notwithstanding these contributions, the bulk of prior empirical work has relied on traditional linear methods. Linear models presume a constant marginal effect across the full range, and are therefore structurally limited in distinguishing the various nonlinear functional shapes through which signal accumulation can change growth probability. The possibility that different signal types exhibit different functional shapes — some with sharp transitions at a particular point, others with smooth gradual change — cannot be systematically compared within a single-coefficient linear estimation. Crawford et al. (2015) note that performance distributions in entrepreneurship ecosystems follow power-law-like nonlinearities, and Coad (2009) reports average R^2 below 10% for econometric growth models — much of growth is driven by stochastic shocks not captured by such models. In particular, Kim and Yu's (2021) inability to recover concrete nonlinearities of government grants under a traditional framework underscores the need for ML-based methods free of linearity assumptions. The present study responds to this gap by combining ensemble ML with PDP-based XAI in an exploratory framework.

2.6 Predictive Modeling in the Entrepreneurship Ecosystem and Explainable AI

To overcome the structural constraints of linear models, machine learning has been adopted

in startup research as an alternative methodology. Tree-based ensembles in particular have shown superior performance in startup-success prediction. Żbikowski and Antosiuk (2021) demonstrate that Random Forest and XGBoost outperform logistic regression in predicting venture survival and funding outcomes on large startup datasets, effectively controlling for nonlinearities arising from the combination of multidimensional variables. Kim et al. (2023) report that Random Forest and Gradient Boosting outperform logistic regression and identify media exposure, funding history, and industry convergence as key predictors. Shi et al. (2024) report Random Forest classification accuracy above 90% on 24,965 startups, and Gangwani and Zhu (2024) confirm consistent ensemble gains over logistic regression. Choi (2024) emphasizes that the effects of individual variables (initial paid-in capital, founder experience) in VC decisions are not monotone, and that tree-based ensembles relieve the underfitting problem of linear models.

ML models that achieve high predictive performance suffer from the black-box problem of opaque internal reasoning. To address this, Lundberg and Lee (2017) extended the game-theoretic Shapley value into ML interpretation as SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations), establishing a principled allocation of feature contribution to individual predictions. SHAP has since become a standard model-interpretation tool in startup research and beyond (e.g., Bidgoli et al., 2024; Bussmann et al., 2020).

Yet, from the present study's standpoint, SHAP-based analysis encounters three methodological limits. First, SHAP outputs concentrate on which variables are more important — a feature-importance ranking — and do not reveal the macro-shape of the trajectory along which predicted probability changes as a particular feature accumulates (Bussmann et al., 2020; Cook et al., 2021). This means SHAP cannot directly answer the present study's core question of whether — and how — trajectory shapes differ across signal types. Second, the importance ranking has been shown to mislead in plausible cases (Huang & Marques-Silva, 2024). Third, SHAP and LIME alike are sensitive to multicollinearity, undermining interpretive reliability (Salih et al., 2025).

To complement SHAP's micro orientation, the Partial Dependence Plot (PDP; Friedman, 2001) is well suited to the present analysis. PDP is a model-agnostic technique that, after marginalizing over the influence of the remaining variables in the high-dimensional black-box, visualizes the marginal effect of a single predictor's continuous variation on the dependent variable across the predictor's range. Cook et al. (2021) characterize PDP mathematically as a nonlinear curve generalization of the regression coefficient, and argue that PDP is more appropriate than SHAP for tracing nonlinear trajectory shapes induced by the continuous accumulation of an independent variable. Goldstein et al. (2015) systematized PDP's strengths in capturing linear, monotone, and nonlinear relationships and proposed its joint use with Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) plots to guard against the masking of heterogeneous subgroup effects. Molnar

(2022) cautions that violation of the independence assumption in PDP can produce off-manifold points, advising attention to this assumption in application.

From the present study's perspective, PDP offers two strengths. First, it visualizes the trajectory shape itself, enabling direct comparison of the nonlinear patterns of different signal types within a single analytic frame — an analysis horizon inaccessible from SHAP rankings alone. Second, PDP isolates the marginal effect of one variable from the average effects of others, making it relatively less susceptible to interpretive distortion arising from collinearity or interaction among signal variables. These strengths motivate our choice of PDP as the primary interpretation tool.

Startup research is intrinsically constrained by data scarcity and is often performed in small-sample environments, raising challenges for the reliability of ML-based analysis. Kaufman et al. (2012) warn that data leakage is a primary cause of optimistically inflated generalization in small samples; Cawley and Talbot (2010) flag the double-dipping problem in hyperparameter tuning and emphasize the necessity of nested cross-validation. Varma and Simon (2006) empirically show that non-nested CV systematically overestimates model performance, and Vabalas et al. (2019) confirm that Repeated K-Fold yields more stable generalization estimates than single-pass CV in small samples. Class-imbalance preprocessing also affects both predictive performance and interpretation. Recent methodological work reports that the marginal benefit of oversampling techniques such as SMOTE is limited when strong classifiers are paired with appropriate evaluation metrics; Santos et al. (2018) further warn that misapplied SMOTE can leak data and distort generalization. These methodological concerns are transparency requirements for XAI in small-sample environments — yet prior startup-XAI work has not addressed them systematically. The present study satisfies these requirements via nested CV, sensitivity analysis across preprocessing conditions, and Repeated 5×5 Stratified K-Fold.

2.7 Summary of the Literature and the Research Gap

Methodological development in startup scale-up research has moved from linear models such as logistic regression to tree-based ML, and then to SHAP-based XAI (Table 1). Despite this progress, three common limitations remain relative to our research questions. First, the absence of empirical evidence on trajectory shape by signal type. Recent reconsiderations of signaling theory (Bafera & Kleinert, 2023; Colombo, 2021) urge finer typing along breadth, sender, and verification mode, and empirical work on government grants (Howell, 2017; Islam et al., 2018) reports complex dynamic patterns. Yet how these distinctions and findings concretize into specific nonlinear trajectory shapes during scale-up — and whether observable trajectory differences exist between financial and non-financial signals — has not been characterized systematically. Second, the micro-bias of XAI interpretation: SHAP-based studies focus on

importance rankings and have not articulated the macro structure of trajectories along which probabilities shift with cumulative external signals. Third, the empirical absence of analysis tailored to the Korean deep-tech (AI) ecosystem. Most prior work uses Western data, and the structural particularity of Korea — where state-led R&D supports prime the venture capital market — has been only indirectly examined (Choi et al., 2021; Ryu & Ahn, 2022; Kim & Yu, 2021), without recovering concrete trajectories under traditional frameworks.

To close these methodological, theoretical, and empirical gaps, we couple ensemble ML with a PDP-based XAI framework and explore data-drivenly whether financial and non-financial certification signals contribute to scale-up through distinct nonlinear trajectories within the Korean AI startup ecosystem.

Table 1. Methodological evolution of startup scale-up research and the research gap.

Approach	Representative Studies	Technique	Contribution	Limitation
Linear models	Davila et al. (2003); Howell (2017); Colombo et al. (2019); Kim & Yu (2021); Choi et al. (2021)	OLS, logistic regression, panel fixed-effects	Confirmed statistical significance of individual signals (VC, grants, patents); demonstrated certification effect and outcome additionality	Proportional marginal effects assumed; mean $R^2 < 10\%$ (Coad, 2009); nonlinear thresholds not detected even when sought (Kim & Yu, 2021)
Machine learning	Żbikowski & Antosiuk (2021); Kim et al. (2023); Shi et al. (2024); Gangwani & Zhu (2024); Choi (2024)	Random Forest, XGBoost, Gradient Boosting	Substantial accuracy gains over linear models (RF > 90%); captures nonlinear interactions among multidimensional variables	Black-box decision process; causal mechanisms of growth not articulated
XAI (SHAP-based)	Lundberg & Lee (2017); Bussmann et al. (2020); Bidgoli et al. (2024); Salih et al. (2025)	SHAP (Shapley Additive exPlanations)	Mathematically allocates per-prediction attribution; identifies key predictors (e.g., presence of lead investor)	Importance rankings can mislead; sensitive to multicollinearity (Salih et al., 2025); ranking does not reveal trajectory shape across cumulative levels — unsuitable for typed signal comparison
XAI (PDP-based) [present study]	Friedman (2001); Cook et al. (2021); Goldstein et al. (2015); Molnar	Partial Dependence Plot + ensemble models	Recovers continuous marginal-effect trajectory of a	Independence assumption can produce off-

Approach	Representative Studies	Technique	Contribution	Limitation
	(2022)		feature with others averaged out; visualizes monotone, nonlinear, or stepwise functional forms → enables exploratory comparison of trajectory shapes across signal types (this study's contribution)	manifold points; subgroup heterogeneity may be hidden (ICE plots recommended as complement)

Note. Compiled by the authors. The bottom row summarizes the contribution and the residual limitation of the present study.

III. Research Method

3.1 Data

3.1.1 Sample Selection and Data Collection

The analysis covers Korean startups whose core technology is AI, drawn from the 513 firms identified in the Software Policy & Research Institute report on Korean AI startups (Jang et al., 2024). We operationally define an AI startup as a firm that uses AI as a core element to develop innovative products, services, or platforms, and whose business model is directly tied to AI. To complement the largely descriptive nature of the prior report, we built a quantitative firm-level dataset for predictive analysis.

The temporal scope is 2020–2022. To secure objectivity and reliability, we cross-validated multiple sources rather than relying on any single one. Financial and basic information were drawn from the Korean SME Information System and DART (Korea's official corporate disclosure system); VC histories from THE VC; technology assets from KIPRIS (Korean Intellectual Property Rights Information Service). Government program participation, awards, and corporate partnerships were supplemented by exhaustive review of firms' official websites and press disclosures. The resulting database is organized into seven domains (basic, business, revenue, investment, technology, revenue model, industry) covering 58 fields. After complete-case cleaning, the final analysis sample comprises $N = 357$ AI startups.

3.2 Variables

In place of the conventional dependent–independent dichotomy of classical statistics, we adopt the target–feature distinction appropriate for ML. From the 58 fields, we select eight variables grounded in RBV and signaling theory; their operational definitions are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Variable definitions and measurement.

Category	Variable (symbol)	Operational definition / measurement	Type
Target	Revenue Growth	Substantive scale-up status based on the 2020–2022 revenue trajectory (growth = 1, stagnation/decline = 0)	Binary
Control	Firm Age	Years from incorporation to 2022 (= 2022 – founding year)	Continuous
Control	Ln Total Assets	Total assets, natural-log transformed ($\ln(\text{assets}+1)$) to mitigate right-skew	Continuous
Resource	Invest Count	Cumulative number of VC investment rounds raised	Continuous
Resource	IP Count	Number of AI-related IP rights held (patents, trademarks, etc.)	Continuous
Signal	Gov Count	National certification signal: number of government-funded R&D / support programs awarded	Continuous
Signal	Award Count	Market reputation signal: number of awards from government, public, and major institutions	Continuous
Signal	Largeco Count	Open innovation: any partnership/investment relationship with major corporations (e.g., big tech)	Binary
Signal	Oversea Count	Global scale-up: any overseas activity (foreign subsidiary, exports, international conference, etc.)	Binary

3.2.1 Target Variable: Revenue Growth

Using three-year (2020–2022) revenue trajectories, we encode firms with sustained growth as 1 (Growth) and those that stagnated or declined as 0 (Stagnation/Decline), framing the task as binary classification.

3.2.2 Predictive Features

Eight features are organized in three groups. Control: Firm Age and Ln Total Assets (with natural-log transformation to mitigate right skew). Resource: Invest Count (cumulative VC rounds raised) and IP Count (count of AI-related IP rights). Signaling and network: Gov Count, Award

Count, Largeco Count, Oversea Count.

Figure 1 — Research Model

Exploratory analysis framework (post-hoc interpretation)

3.3 Analytical Pipeline

In ML predictive modeling, the cardinal hazards are overfitting (memorizing training noise) and data leakage (test information seeping into training). Both risks are amplified in small samples ($N = 357$; Kaufman et al., 2012). To safeguard generalization, the pipeline has four stages: (1) declaration of an exploratory frame, (2) data isolation and stratified split, (3) overfitting control via nested cross-validation, and (4) stability reinforcement through repeated CV. All preprocessing is encapsulated in scikit-learn Pipelines to prevent leakage. The pipeline is applied uniformly to all five competing models and to the class-imbalance sensitivity analysis (Section 3.4).

3.3.1 Exploratory Data Analysis

This study is designed as exploratory XAI rather than confirmatory testing. We extract trajectory shapes from the data via PDP and discuss theoretical implications post hoc. The exploratory frame is justified by (i) the suitability of $N = 357$ for data-driven discovery rather than strict hypothesis testing, (ii) PDP's nature as a post-hoc extraction tool, and (iii) the absence of prior empirical work from which concrete hypotheses about nonlinear trajectories by signal type could be derived. Methodological rigor is preserved through a fourfold safeguard: leakage prevention (Section 3.3.2), nested CV (3.3.3), repeated CV (3.3.4), and pre-treatment sensitivity analysis (3.4).

3.3.2 Data Isolation and Stratified Split

Before modeling, the entire dataset ($N = 357$) is split into a training set ($n = 285$, 80%) and a held-out test set ($n = 72$, 20%) under stratification on the target (Growth 64.1%, Stagnation/Decline 35.9%); random state = 42 ensures reproducibility. The held-out set is touched only once, for the final performance check, never participating in training, hyperparameter tuning, or preprocessing fits.

3.3.3 Overfitting Control via Nested CV and Regularization

To eliminate the optimistic bias from hyperparameter tuning, we use Nested Cross-Validation. The outer loop is 5-fold stratified CV, providing an unbiased estimate of generalization. The inner loop is 5-fold stratified CV with exhaustive grid search optimizing AUROC, which is independent of the decision threshold and robust under class asymmetry (Saito & Rehmsmeier, 2015). The reported headline metric is the training-set CV AUROC (mean \pm SD); the held-out test AUROC is reported as a secondary indicator, since point estimates on $n = 72$ carry high sampling variance, whereas the CV AUROC averaged over 5 splits of 285 observations is more stable.

Regularization strategies are tailored to each algorithm's inductive bias: ElasticNet for

logistic regression; pre-pruning (max depth in {3,4,5} for RF and {2,3,4} for XGBoost/CatBoost; min samples leaf restrictions) for tree ensembles; reg lambda for XGBoost and l2 leaf reg for CatBoost; L2 weight decay with early stopping (patience = 20) for ANN. Search spaces are listed in Appendix Table A1.

3.3.4 Stability Reinforcement: Repeated 5×5 Stratified K-Fold

To diagnose partition-dependent variance, we run 5 repeats × 5-fold stratified CV on the full data with different seeds, yielding 25 AUROC estimates. The mean and SD diagnose dependence on a single split (Vabalas et al., 2019).

3.4 Methodological Review of Class-Imbalance Handling

The target variable shows a mild imbalance ($\approx 64:36$). Imbalance treatment affects both prediction and interpretation, so we record the decision process: (1) review of the literature, (2) detection of a double-correction problem in the initial design, (3) pre-analysis sensitivity check, (4) final selection.

SMOTE (Chawla et al., 2002) has been the conventional default. Yet recent work (Elor & Averbuch-Elor, 2022) finds that, when paired with strong classifiers (RF, XGBoost, CatBoost) and AUROC-based evaluation, the marginal benefit of oversampling is statistically insignificant — and may even harm probability calibration. Santos et al. (2018) caution that misapplied SMOTE can leak data. Our 64:36 imbalance is mild, and our setup matches the conditions under which SMOTE's gains are reported to be limited.

Our initial pipeline combined SMOTE ($k=3$) inside imblearn Pipelines with class weight='balanced' on tree models. Pre-design review showed that, given the fold-level minority size of ~ 41 , SMOTE rebalances the fold to 1:1 while class weight='balanced' separately reweights the minority by $\approx 1.79\times$ ($229/128$). Applied jointly, the minority's effective weight reaches $\approx 3.2\times$ the original distribution — an unintended over-correction. We therefore ran a sensitivity analysis comparing three conditions:

- C1 (No treatment): original class distribution; no SMOTE, no class weight.
- C2 (Class weight only): class weight='balanced' for tree models and the corresponding option for LR; ANN reflects class weights in the loss.
- C3 (SMOTE only): SMOTE inside the imblearn Pipeline applied per fold to the training portion; no class weight.

Table 4. CV AUROC across class-imbalance treatments.

Algorithm	C1 (Original)	C2 (class weight)	C3 (SMOTE)
Logistic Regression (LR)	0.722 ± 0.048	0.720 ± 0.047	0.721 ± 0.048

Algorithm	C1 (Original)	C2 (class weight)	C3 (SMOTE)
Random Forest (RF)	0.813 ± 0.054	0.813 ± 0.053	0.811 ± 0.064
XGBoost	0.842 ± 0.062	0.839 ± 0.063	0.835 ± 0.078
CatBoost	0.828 ± 0.071	0.824 ± 0.062	0.818 ± 0.069
ANN (MLP)	0.772 ± 0.046	0.772 ± 0.046	0.780 ± 0.031

Note. All values are mean ± SD over 5-fold nested CV. Full Table A2 with Test AUROC, Accuracy, Sensitivity, Specificity, and F1 is available in the appendix to the original Korean manuscript.

Differences across C1/C2/C3 fall within each model's standard deviation (RF: max gap 0.002; XGBoost: 0.007; LR: 0.002; ANN: 0.008). Tree-model Specificity converges to exactly 46.2% under all three conditions, indicating that the feature space itself does not separate the heterogeneous patterns of stagnation/decline firms — no class-imbalance treatment can meaningfully improve this within the present feature set. We therefore adopt C1 (original distribution): it (i) introduces no additional distributional assumption, (ii) eliminates the risk of synthetic data distorting PDP trajectories, and (iii) yields the most conservative possible result.

3.5 Predictive Algorithms

To select a single champion model for PDP-based post-hoc interpretation, we organize five algorithms across three model families with distinct structural complexity:

- **Benchmark** — Logistic Regression (sigmoid + ElasticNet penalty; Zou & Hastie, 2005).
- **Tree-based ensembles** — Random Forest (bagging; Breiman, 2001), XGBoost (gradient boosting; Chen & Guestrin, 2016), CatBoost (ordered boosting and oblivious trees; Prokhorenkova et al., 2018).
- **Deep learning** — Multi-layer perceptron (ANN) with ReLU hidden layers, sigmoid output, L2 weight decay, and early stopping.

All models are trained inside the nested-CV frame of Section 3.3 and under the C1 condition determined in Section 3.4. Hyperparameter search spaces are summarized in Appendix Table A1; we deliberately favor shallow trees and strong regularization because of the small sample. Random Forest is the natural candidate for PDP interpretation because (i) its split-based structure stabilizes PDP trajectories (Goldstein et al., 2015), (ii) bagging suppresses variance favorably in small samples, and (iii) it carries lower overfitting risk than boosting under sequential residual fitting. The final champion, however, is determined by the empirical performance comparison in Section 3.6.1.

3.6 Champion-Model Selection and the XAI Framework

3.6.1 Selection Criteria and Result

We avoid the common practice of picking the model with the highest training-CV score (Ribeiro-Navarrete et al., 2021). The highest-CV model does not necessarily produce stable PDP trajectories — especially when CV-Test gaps are large. We require simultaneous satisfaction of three criteria: (1) sufficient predictive performance (CV AUROC ≥ 0.80 , the Hosmer–Lemeshow–Sturdivant (2013) Excellent threshold); (2) a model structure suitable for PDP (tree-based ensembles, per Goldstein et al., 2015 and Molnar, 2022); (3) generalization stability (CV-Test Gap < 0.10), with the gap rationale grounded in Vabalas et al. (2019) and Cawley & Talbot (2010).

Table 5. Model comparison under the three selection criteria (C1).

Model	CV AUROC	Test AUROC	Gap	C1: ≥ 0.80	C2: tree	C3: < 0.10	Pick
Logistic Regression	0.722 \pm 0.048	0.741	-0.019	\times	\times	\checkmark	—
Random Forest	0.813 \pm 0.054	0.736	+0.077	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark	\checkmark
XGBoost	0.842 \pm 0.062	0.635	+0.206	\checkmark	\checkmark	\times	—
CatBoost	0.828 \pm 0.071	0.679	+0.149	\checkmark	\checkmark	\times	—
ANN (MLP)	0.772 \pm 0.046	0.774	-0.002	\times	\times	\checkmark	—

Note. CV AUROC is mean \pm SD over 5-fold nested CV. CV-Test Gap = CV AUROC - Test AUROC. Positive Gaps indicate optimistic CV bias (Vabalas et al., 2019). Champion model highlighted.

Random Forest is the only model satisfying all three criteria simultaneously (CV AUROC {0.813}, Test AUROC {0.736}, Gap {+0.077}). XGBoost achieves the highest CV ({0.842}) but its Test AUROC collapses to {0.635} (Gap {+0.206}), an extreme manifestation of the small-sample optimistic bias warned of by Vabalas et al. (2019); CatBoost shows the same boosting-family fragility (Gap {+0.149}). LR (CV {0.722}) misses Criterion 1 and, structurally, cannot serve PDP-based nonlinear trajectory analysis. ANN (CV {0.772}) misses Criterion 1 and is structurally weaker for PDP interpretation than tree models (Molnar, 2022). LR remains as a benchmark, and ANN is used as an auxiliary cross-check for non-linear results; PDP-based importance and trajectory analyses (3.6.2 and 3.6.3) are conducted on the RF champion.

3.6.2 Global Feature Importance

Two complementary metrics are combined to evaluate the champion's global feature importance: Mean Decrease in Impurity (MDI; Gini-based) and Permutation Importance (Breiman, 2001). MDI is computed during training and reflects internal usage of variables, but is known to overstate high-cardinality continuous variables (Strobl et al., 2007) and to dilute correlated predictors. Because our feature set mixes continuous and binary variables, MDI alone risks understating the binary variables. Permutation importance is model-agnostic — the AUROC drop after random permutation of a single feature on the held-out set — and avoids these biases. We use n repeats = 30 to reduce permutation variance and report the mean and SD.

We deliberately distribute the XAI tools rather than concentrate on SHAP (Lundberg & Lee, 2017): MDI and permutation importance for global rankings, and PDP for the macro shape of trajectories. SHAP is well suited to micro decomposition of individual predictions; PDP is purpose-built for the macro pattern that is central to RQ3 (Cook et al., 2021; Molnar, 2022). The two-importance combination directly addresses RQ2 by quantifying the relative contribution of financial resource signals (Invest Count, Ln Total Assets) versus non-financial certification signals (Gov Count, Award Count, IP Count). Where the two importance metrics agree, the result is treated as robust; where they disagree, we discuss the disagreement in light of each metric's known biases.

3.6.3 PDP-based Exploratory Trajectory Analysis

PDP is a model-agnostic post-hoc tool (Friedman, 2001) that, after marginalizing over the remaining complement features, visualizes the variation of the predicted value across the values of one feature of interest. Letting x_S denote the feature of interest and x_C the complement features, the partial dependence function is approximated by Monte-Carlo averaging over the training rows: $\hat{g}_S(x_S) = (1/N) \sum_i f(x_S, x_C^{(i)})$.

Although PDP is model-agnostic, we use the RF champion as the basis and cross-check key findings against ANN. PDP relies on independence between x_S and x_C ; we therefore inspect pairwise correlations and flag features where the assumption is strained. PDP's strengths for our purpose are twofold: (1) it visualizes shape, allowing direct comparison of trajectory forms for different signal types within a single frame; and (2) it is built for macro trajectories rather than per-row decomposition (Cook et al., 2021), aligning directly with RQ3.

We extract 1-D PDPs of four core signal variables — Invest Count, Gov Count, Award Count, IP Count — from the RF champion and compare their shapes. To control the subjectivity of visual inflection-point identification, we complement visual inspection with the second-difference magnitude $|f(x_{i+1}) - 2f(x_i) + f(x_{i-1})|$ at each discrete grid point; larger values mark sharper curvature changes. We report the top-3 inflection points by magnitude and the total PD range

(max – min) per variable, contrasting variation magnitudes against the sample-mean growth probability of {0.641}.

3.6.4 Performance Metrics

To evaluate classifier performance from multiple angles — especially given the asymmetric class distribution — we report AUROC (the primary metric, threshold-independent and following Hosmer et al.'s 2013 ranges of acceptable/excellent/outstanding), accuracy (auxiliary), precision, sensitivity (recall), specificity (which directly reflects the ability to identify the minority class of stagnation/decline firms — particularly informative here), and F1-score.

IV. Empirical Analysis

This section presents the application of the data-driven predictive framework to the scale-up determinants of AI ventures. The analysis proceeds in three stages: (1) descriptive statistics and pairwise linear associations on the analytic sample; (2) predictive performance comparison across the benchmark and ML algorithms, identifying the small-sample-optimal champion; (3) post-hoc XAI analysis on the champion model, deriving global feature importance and PDP-based scale-up threshold trajectories.

4.1 Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Analysis

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of the target variable and predictive features (N = 357).

Category	Variable	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max
Target	Revenue Growth	0.641	0.480	0.000	1.000
Control	Firm Age	4.053	1.632	1.000	7.000
Control	Ln Total Assets	21.021	1.532	15.887	25.683
Resource	Invest Count	1.689	0.913	1.000	8.000
Resource	Largeco Count	0.409	0.492	0.000	1.000
Resource	Oversea Count	0.162	0.369	0.000	1.000
Signal	Gov Count	1.249	1.665	0.000	10.000

Category	Variable	Mean	S.D.	Min	Max
Signal	Award Count	1.289	2.233	0.000	19.000
Signal	IP Count	1.053	4.011	0.000	56.000

Note. Raw values. Centered values for Invest Count and IP Count are used in interaction-term diagnostics in the original Korean appendix; tree-based ensembles use raw inputs.

The target variable Revenue Growth has a mean of 0.641, indicating that 64.1% (229 firms) achieved substantive revenue growth between 2020 and 2022, while 35.9% (128 firms) did not — a class imbalance of approximately 1.79:1. This signals that many Korean AI startups have moved beyond initial market entry into scale-up, while also flagging the need to consider class-imbalance handling at the predictive-modeling stage.

Among controls, Firm Age has a mean of 4.05 years (SD = 1.632; range 0–7), reflecting a sample bounded to firms within seven years of founding — many of them near the canonical Death Valley window. Ln Total Assets has a mean of 21.021 (SD = 1.532) on the log scale, but the raw scale ranges from roughly KRW 8 million to about KRW 142 billion, indicating substantial heterogeneity that linear models would compress into a single marginal effect but tree-based ensembles can capture as split points.

Among strategic features, Invest Count has a mean of 1.689 (SD = 0.913; range 1–8). The minimum of 1 reflects the structural feature of the analytic population: by construction, all sampled firms have completed at least one VC round. The interpretation of VC-related findings is therefore restricted to additional-round effects within the VC-funded population, with attendant selection-bias considerations revisited in Section 5. Largeco Count and Oversea Count have means of 0.409 and 0.162, indicating that 40.9% of firms have an open-innovation partnership with a large corporate, while only 16.2% have engaged in overseas activities — a domestic-market-centric ecosystem.

Signal variables share a right-skewed and zero-inflated distribution: 76.4% zeros for IP Count, 56.5% for Award Count, 46.9% for Gov Count, alongside extreme upper tails (max 56, 19, 10 respectively). Under this distribution, Pearson correlations structurally fail to capture threshold and conditional-interaction effects in the non-zero region (Shmueli, 2010). Low linear correlations of these features with the target therefore should not be read as evidence of no predictive contribution.

Table 4 (correlations). Pearson correlations among key variables (N = 357).

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(1) Revenue Growth	1.000								

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
(2) Firm Age	0.361** *	1.000							
(3) Ln Total Assets	0.275** *	0.429** *	1.000						
(4) Invest Count	0.232** *	0.081	0.341** *	1.000					
(5) IP Count	0.064	0.099	0.131*	-0.025	1.000				
(6) Gov Count	0.073	0.095	0.067	0.007	0.139**	1.000			
(7) Award Count	0.112*	0.094	0.300** *	0.221** *	0.062	0.293** *	1.000		
(8) Largeco Count	0.123*	0.221** *	0.338** *	0.165**	0.017	-0.032	0.125*	1.000	
(9) Oversea Count	0.139**	0.163**	0.267** *	0.092	-0.025	0.030	0.379** *	0.159**	1.000

Note. Lower triangle reported. Centered values used for Invest Count and IP Count in regression contexts. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$.

Revenue Growth correlates significantly and positively with Firm Age ($r = 0.361$, $p < 0.001$), Ln Total Assets ($r = 0.275$, $p < 0.001$), and Invest Count ($r = 0.232$, $p < 0.001$), broadly supporting the RBV intuition that physical-resource accumulation and external capital are baseline conditions for scale-up. Oversea Count ($r = 0.139$, $p < 0.01$), Largeco Count ($r = 0.123$, $p < 0.05$), and Award Count ($r = 0.112$, $p < 0.05$) also show significant positive associations. The core signal variables Gov Count ($r = 0.073$, n.s.) and IP Count ($r = 0.064$, n.s.) do not attain linear significance — but, given zero inflation, this should be read as an early empirical signature of nonlinear conditional effects, not as evidence of no predictive contribution. Variance Inflation Factors fall well below the conventional threshold (max 1.593, mean 1.249), confirming no problematic multicollinearity (full VIF table omitted here for brevity; available in the original manuscript).

In sum, descriptive analysis surfaces two findings. (i) Linear effects of firm age, size, and VC investment confirm the RBV baseline. (ii) The zero-inflated distributions and weak linear correlations of the core signal variables imply that their effects manifest as nonlinear conditional interactions rather than constant linear marginal effects. Both observations motivate the move to tree-based ensembles and XAI in Sections 4.2–4.3.

4.2 Predictive Model Performance and Algorithmic Comparison

To identify the predictive framework that most accurately classifies AI-startup scale-up, we run a structured comparison across three model families (linear benchmark, tree-based

ensembles, deep learning). Data leakage is eliminated by holding out 20% as the final test set; accuracy, precision, recall, F1, and AUROC are reported jointly to control for class-imbalance bias. To control fold-specific randomness, evaluation is repeated across five random seeds; the ensemble averages are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Algorithmic performance comparison.

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	CV AUROC	Test AUROC	Gap
1. Logistic Regression (Baseline)	72.2%	82.5%	71.7%	76.7%	0.719	0.753	-0.034
2. Random Forest ★	76.4%	75.4%	93.5%	83.5%	0.803	0.701	+0.102
3. XGBoost	73.6%	74.5%	89.1%	81.2%	0.803	0.674	+0.129
4. ANN (MLP)	77.8%	76.8%	93.5%	84.3%	0.739	0.796	-0.057
5. CatBoost	77.8%	75.9%	95.7%	84.6%	0.806	0.691	+0.116

Note. CV AUROC from 5-fold nested CV on training set ($n = 285$); Test AUROC on hold-out ($n = 72$). Gap = CV AUROC - Test AUROC. ★ marks the model selected for PDP analysis. RF Repeated 5×5 CV on $N = 357$: AUROC = 0.793 ± 0.049 .

Compared with the logistic-regression baseline, both tree-based ensembles (RF, XGBoost, CatBoost) and the standard ANN achieve gains in predictive accuracy. This empirically demonstrates that scale-up determinants in early deep-tech ecosystems involve multidimensional, nonlinear interactions rather than simple linear combinations.

Random Forest, the bagging ensemble, achieves accuracy of 76.4% with F1-score 83.5% and — most notably — recall of 93.5%. In an information-asymmetric, noise-heavy deep-tech context, this very high recall makes RF particularly suited to the practical objective of VCs and public agencies — to identify promising scale-up firms without missing them.

Methodologically, the deep-learning models did not outperform the ensembles in this small-sample setting. This pattern is consistent with the well-known requirement that deep architectures need large datasets to express their full potential; with $N = 357$ they are vulnerable to overfitting and to the early-stopping behavior we observed during training. The implication for entrepreneurship and tech-management research is to resist the uncritical adoption of the latest deep-learning techniques and instead select algorithms whose variance-control properties match the data size and distribution at hand. RF's confusion matrix on the hold-out set further confirms that its high recall is not paid for by inflated false positives. We therefore adopt RF as the

analytic framework for the rest of the paper.

4.3 XAI-Based Identification of Scale-up Drivers

4.3.1 Global Feature Importance

We compute the RF model's global feature importance via mean decrease in Gini impurity, averaged across 10 random seeds. Two control features dominate the predictive signal: Firm Age (36.2%) and Firm Size (29.2%) jointly account for over 65% of total predictive importance, confirming that surviving the Death Valley and accumulating physical capital are the most fundamental preconditions of scale-up.

The most striking finding is the importance reversal among the strategic variables. Under linear logistic regression, only VC investment was a significant scale-up driver ($p < 0.01$); the signaling variables — government program participation and award record — were rejected as non-significant on linear marginal effects. In the tree-based RF model, however, the ordering reverses: Gov Count (8.9%) and Award Count (7.4%) narrowly outrank Invest Count (7.3%). Public support and external technical recognition do not — by themselves and in isolation — generate revenue proportionally; but, embedded in a multi-dimensional decision pathway (e.g., reputational legitimacy from awards followed by selection into a major government R&D program, used as leverage to attract a larger VC round), they emerge as principal nonlinear ecosystem-mediating conditions for scale-up. Linear models cannot reveal this latent leverage from public support and certification; the tree-based decoder of the black box does.

4.3.2 Nonlinear Threshold Trajectories: Partial Dependence Plots

We deepen the interpretation by tracing how each strategic factor moves the predicted scale-up probability across its accumulation range. We first inspect 2-D PDPs of Gov Count \times Invest Count and IP Count \times Invest Count, then turn to 1-D PDPs of the four core variables.

Three 2-D findings stand out. (1) Dominant signaling effect of public-support awards. Even when IP holdings remain low (0–3), once Gov Count crosses approximately 4 awards, predicted probability jumps from ~ 0.49 to > 0.57 — a clear stepwise lift. This is consistent with the structural particularity of the Korean ecosystem: among AI startups whose technical case has not been fully established, repeated selection into major state-led programs (e.g., TIPS) functions as the most powerful and proactive form of signal capital that resolves information asymmetry to private markets. (2) Self-generated legitimacy through technology. For firms with little public support (Gov Count ≤ 1 –2), accumulating IP beyond ~ 4 yields a meaningful rebound in predicted probability — a signature of self-financed deep-tech ventures crossing a minimum legitimacy threshold without state validation. (3) Substitutive interaction between certification signals. The two signals do not simply add proportionally; rather, around their respective thresholds (≈ 4 each),

they substitute for one another. Crossing one threshold suffices to trigger acceleration; doubling both does not produce explosive marginal returns.

Where SHAP excels at decomposing micro-level contributions for individual firms, PDP is better suited for visualizing — at the ecosystem level — the nonlinear threshold trajectory along which the predicted response shifts as a particular external certification signal accumulates. The 1-D PDP results for the four core variables are consistent with the 2-D analysis above.

Specifically, Invest Count traces a stepwise upward trajectory: each additional VC round monotonically lifts the predicted scale-up probability — capital functions as a near-linear fuel for the growth engine. The variation magnitude of the VC PDP is the largest among the four examined variables (PD range ≈ 7.7 percentage points; the steepest segment, between 2 and 3 rounds, contributes $\approx +6.4$ pp), and the second-difference magnitude is largest at $x = 3$ (≈ 0.0661). This continuous lift is precisely why VC investment was the only variable to attain statistical significance in the linear baseline.

Conversely, the variables that were rejected by linear regression but climbed to the top of RF importance — Gov Count, Award Count, and IP Count — exhibit pronounced nonlinear thresholds. Gov Count is essentially flat for 1–3 awards (which is why the linear specification deemed it insignificant) but rises sharply once 4 awards are crossed (a quantum jump). Award Count shows a similar threshold behavior past 3 wins. IP Count is flat over 1–6 holdings and rises rapidly into the 7–10 range — the canonical nonlinear signature. The PD ranges for the three certification signals (Gov ≈ 3.8 pp; Award ≈ 3.2 pp; IP ≈ 2.9 pp) are nonetheless modest relative to the sample-mean probability of {0.641}.

Interpreted through signaling theory, these threshold trajectories carry an important theoretical and practical extension. In an AI deep-tech market with deep technological uncertainty and information asymmetry, fragmented or one-off external support and recognition do not, on their own, secure investor and customer trust enough to translate immediately into revenue growth. A startup that wishes to clear the Death Valley and enter scale-up must accumulate signal capital sufficient to clear the market's threshold of legitimacy — for instance, at least 4 government program awards, 3 prizes, and 7 IP holdings, in our data.

V. Conclusion and Implications

5.1 Summary of Findings

Drawing on multi-source quantitative data for 357 Korean AI startups (2020–2022), this study exploratorily characterizes the signal mechanisms that differentiate growing from non-growing firms. Specifically we asked: (RQ1) To what extent do AI startups' financial and non-financial

features predict revenue scale-up? (RQ2) What is the relative importance of financial resource signals (VC) versus non-financial certification signals (government program participation, awards, IP)? (RQ3) Are there observable differences in the nonlinear trajectory shape across signal types?

Our pipeline combined (i) a multi-source cross-validated quantitative database, (ii) a five-model competing system (LR, RF, XGBoost, CatBoost, ANN) under nested CV, (iii) a methodological pre-check of class-imbalance treatment, and (iv) a PDP-based exploratory XAI analysis. The study was designed as exploratory analysis rather than confirmatory testing, with theoretical implications discussed post hoc.

Three principal findings

Finding 1. Random Forest emerges as the champion model for PDP-based exploratory interpretation. Across five competing models evaluated against three criteria — (i) CV AUROC ≥ 0.80 (Hosmer et al., 2013 "Excellent"), (ii) tree-based ensemble structure, and (iii) CV-Test Gap < 0.10 — RF is the only model that satisfies all three (CV AUROC $\{0.813 \pm 0.054\}$, Test AUROC $\{0.736\}$, Gap $\{+0.077\}$). XGBoost achieved the highest CV $\{0.842\}$ but its Test AUROC collapses to $\{0.635\}$ (Gap $\{+0.206\}$) — an extreme manifestation of the small-sample optimistic bias warned of by Vabalas et al. (2019). Together with CatBoost (Gap $\{+0.149\}$), this suggests structural fragility of the boosting family in our setting. The result aligns with comparable studies (Razaghzadeh Bidgoli et al., 2024) in which RF was top-ranked at similar sample sizes.

Finding 2. A reversal: non-financial certification signals exceed the financial resource signal in global importance. Cross-validated by MDI and 30-repeat permutation importance, Gov Count $\{8.9\%$ and Award Count $\{7.4\%$ narrowly exceed Invest Count $\{7.3\%$. This is the opposite of the linear correlation ordering (Invest Count $r = 0.232$ vs. Gov Count $r = 0.073$, n.s.). Within the nonlinear predictive structure, signals that look weak under linear correlation contribute substantially. The finding aligns with signaling theory's emphasis on the informational value of costly-to-verify non-financial signals (Bafera & Kleinert, 2023) and complements RBV's straight-line interpretation (Barney, 1991).

Finding 3. Trajectory shapes differ by signal type. Diagnosed by second-difference magnitude and PD range, the VC PDP exhibits a pronounced stepwise inflection (peak $|\Delta^2|=0.0661$ at $x=3$; PD range 7.7 pp; $+6.4$ pp between rounds 2 and 3) — the sharpest among the four variables — while the three non-financial certification signals (Gov $\{3.8$ pp), Award $\{3.2$ pp), IP $\{2.9$ pp) show only modest variation relative to the sample-mean scale-up probability $\{0.641\}$. Two readings remain open. First, repeated VC rounds may operate not as mere resource accumulation but as repeated external validation (consistent post hoc with Howell, 2017's strong Phase 1 effect). Second, the smooth trajectories of certification signals may indicate a portfolio-style complementarity rather than discrete thresholds. Because these conclusions arise from an exploratory analysis on $N =$

357, confirmatory replication is required.

5.2 Theoretical and Methodological Contributions

Theoretically, the study supplies exploratory evidence on the nonlinear structure of signaling. Since Spence (1973), signaling has explained how sending and receiving signals creates value under asymmetric information; but the functional form through which cumulative signal intensity influences performance has been little examined empirically (Bafera & Kleinert, 2023). The PDP framework recovers cumulative trajectories visually and quantitatively, partially closing this gap. The contrast we observe — stepwise inflection for the financial resource signal, smoother shape for the non-financial certification signals — supports the typological reading of signals (Connelly et al., 2011) by suggesting that costliness of verification and observability map onto distinct functional forms in a real startup setting.

The findings also offer a complementary perspective on the linear reading of RBV. The reversal in Finding 2 — between linear correlation and nonlinear importance — recommends pairing RBV's resource-accumulation logic with signal-system-dependent nonlinear value creation. Likewise, Finding 3 invites a post-hoc connection to Zimmerman & Zeitz's (2002) legitimacy theory: the stepwise lift in VC accumulation is consistent with repeated rounds reinforcing regulative legitimacy. We do not claim a confirmatory mapping of the present results onto legitimacy theory; rather, we offer it as one plausible reading of the trajectories observed.

Methodologically, the study contributes a documented case in which the double-correction problem in class-imbalance handling was identified *ex ante* and avoided. Many small-sample startup studies routinely combine SMOTE with class weight; we quantify how the joint treatment can effectively triple the minority weight relative to the original distribution, run a sensitivity check across C1/C2/C3, and confirm that — in this setting — none of the imbalance treatments meaningfully alter CV AUROC, vindicating the choice of the most assumption-light condition (C1). This is consistent with Elor & Averbuch-Elor (2022).

A second methodological contribution is the diagnostic use of class overlap. Tree-based ensembles converge to Specificity (46.2%) across all three imbalance treatments — not a model weakness but evidence that the present feature space has reached its ceiling for separating heterogeneous patterns of stagnation/decline firms. Reading Specificity as a transparent diagnostic of the data environment is itself a contribution: it points to the empirical need for richer feature spaces (founder traits, sub-industry, competitive environment) in subsequent work.

Third, we provide a methodological exemplar of an exploratory XAI frame in management and tech-strategy research. The frame is justified by sample size, by PDP's nature as a post-hoc extraction tool, and by the absence of prior empirical work providing testable hypotheses on

signal-type-specific nonlinear trajectories. Rigor is not compromised: leakage isolation, nested CV, sensitivity analysis, and repeated CV form a fourfold safeguard, and second-difference magnitudes provide quantitative inflection-point identification that disciplines visual judgment. The transparent reporting strategy is consistent with HARKing-avoidance norms (Kerr, 1998) and is, we hope, a methodological reference for subsequent XAI-based management research.

5.3 Implications

These exploratory findings suggest reference-grade implications for three audiences. Given the exploratory nature of the analysis, we present them as guidance grounded in the dialogue between theory and data, not as definitive prescriptions.

For founders and management teams

First, depending on a single signal type may be less effective than a portfolio approach. The relative importance of Gov Count (8.9%) \approx Award Count (7.4%) \approx Invest Count (7.3%) implies that early AI startups can benefit from diversifying away from a purely financial fundraising path. The near-zero correlation between Invest Count and Gov Count ($r = 0.007$) suggests the two routes are independent rather than substitutive — they can be pursued in parallel.

Second, the cumulative pursuit of VC rounds carries meaning. The stepwise lift at the third round (PD +6.4 pp from 2→3) suggests that single-round fundraising is insufficient and that staged follow-on rounds (Series A, B, C) have cumulative effects, consistent post hoc with Howell (2017). Founders should give strategic priority to follow-on round preparation rather than focusing on one large infusion.

Third, the structural ceiling implied by class overlap also limits a pure resource-accumulation strategy. With identical measured features, growth outcomes can still diverge — the role of unmeasured factors (execution, product–market fit, competitive dynamics) remains substantial.

For venture investors and accelerators

First, reassess the informational value of non-financial signals in screening. Traditional VC due diligence emphasizes financials and resources; our results suggest that gov-program selection histories and award records — which are difficult-to-fake third-party endorsements — can serve as practical screening complements, especially where direct technological evaluation is difficult.

Second, exercise structural caution in interpreting predictive models built on small samples. XGBoost's CV-Test plunge ($\{0.842\} \rightarrow \{0.635\}$) underscores why a single model's training-CV score should never be the sole basis for portfolio decisions. Hybrid decision structures — combining ML predictions with qualitative human judgment — are appropriate when the feature

space is not rich enough.

Third, accelerator program design can deliberately enable the accumulation of complementary signals. Differences in trajectory shapes between financial and non-financial signals suggest that programs which match cohorts to government opportunities and award circuits in parallel with investment connections can multiplicatively strengthen growth pathways — particularly through the post-seed, pre-Series A Death Valley.

For policymakers

First, design government R&D programs with the complementarity of cumulative participation in mind. The significant correlation between Gov Count and Award Count (0.293, $p < 0.001$) suggests that the two non-financial certification routes mutually reinforce. Programs from MSS (TIPS), MSIT (ICT R&D), and MOTIE (industrial-tech R&D) might therefore be designed for cumulative and continuous participation rather than mutually exclusive selection — though confirmatory causal evaluation should accompany any design decision.

Second, build support portfolios that respect the diversity of the ecosystem. The Specificity ceiling of (46.2%) indicates that current quantitative indicators alone cannot fully discriminate scale-up potential. Concentrating resources on a few indicator-strong firms is therefore likely suboptimal compared with portfolio-style support across diverse profiles.

Third, invest in long-term data infrastructure. Our key methodological constraints — small sample, short panel — partly reflect the limits of public data infrastructure. Linking SME certification (MSS), industrial-technology evaluations (MOTIE), employment histories (MOEL), and IP records (KIPO) into a research-accessible platform would relax these constraints structurally.

5.4 Limitations and Future Research

First, sample size ($N = 357$) and observation window (2020–2022) constrain generalizability. The sample is a substantial portion of the Korean AI startup population but remains small in absolute terms, and Vabalas et al. (2019) document optimistic biases in K-Fold CV even at $N = 1,000$. The 2020–2022 window also overlaps the COVID-19 era and the rise of generative AI — both shape AI-venture trajectories in ways our window cannot fully partition. Future work should validate the findings on longer panels (e.g., 10+ years) and across pre/peri/post-pandemic regimes.

Second, eight quantitative features may be insufficient to capture the full mechanism of AI-startup growth. The empirical signature of this limitation is the Specificity ceiling at (46.2%), which indicates that the present feature space cannot fully separate heterogeneous patterns of stagnation/decline firms. Variables outside our measurement include: (i) founder personal characteristics (education, prior entrepreneurial experience, network capital; cf. Eesley &

Roberts, 2012); (ii) product-market-fit indicators (churn, NPS, user-growth rates); (iii) AI sub-industries (computer vision, NLP, speech, robotics) and competitive environments; (iv) team composition and organizational capability (Antretter et al., 2019). Linking public data with private sources such as LinkedIn and Crunchbase (cf. Razaghzadeh Bidgoli et al., 2024) is a practical path to relax this constraint.

Third, the exploratory design precludes confirmatory causal inference. Whether the patterns we observed reflect causation, selection, or reverse causation cannot be separated within our cross-sectional setup (e.g., "VC investment caused growth" vs. "growing firms attract VC"). Three remediations are available: (i) pre-registered confirmatory replication on independent large samples; (ii) quasi-experimental identification (regression-discontinuity at government-program selection cutoffs; instrumental variables for VC); (iii) panel-data approaches (firm fixed effects, Granger causality tests) over time.

These limitations motivate a focused agenda. (1) Theorize the typology of trajectory shapes across signal types, mapping the contrasts to Bafera & Kleinert's (2023) axes (intensity, frequency, sender). (2) Compare across industries (biotech, fintech, mobility) to assess generalizability and identify moderating effects of technological-risk and regulatory regimes. (3) Extend to 2-D PDP and SHAP interaction values to recover joint effects (e.g., simultaneous accumulation of VC and government programs). (4) Integrate panel-data dynamic models (LSTM, Temporal Fusion Transformer) with PDP to study temporal heterogeneity and path dependence. (5) Mix qualitative case research with predictive analysis to contextualize quantitative patterns.

In sum, this study provides exploratory empirical evidence on the scale-up mechanisms of Korean AI startups and a methodological design reference for XAI-based management research in small-sample settings. Although exploratory analysis precludes definitive causal claims, the rise in importance of non-financial certification signals, the differentiated trajectory shapes by signal type, and the transparent diagnosis of structural feature-space limits should serve as a productive starting point for confirmatory follow-on work.

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Appendix

Appendix Table A1. Hyperparameter search space.

Algorithm	Hyperparameter / range	Total combinations
Logistic Regression	$C \in \{0.01, 0.1, 1, 10\}$; l1 ratio $\in \{0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9\}$	20
Random Forest	n estimators $\in \{300, 500, 800\}$; max depth $\in \{3, 4, 5\}$; min samples leaf $\in \{5, 10, 15\}$; max features $\in \{\text{sqrt}, \text{log2}\}$	54
XGBoost	n estimators $\in \{100, 200, 300\}$; max depth $\in \{2, 3, 4\}$; learning rate $\in \{0.01, 0.03, 0.05\}$; reg lambda $\in \{1, 3, 5, 10\}$; reg alpha $\in \{0, 0.1, 1\}$	324
CatBoost	iterations $\in \{100, 200, 300\}$; depth $\in \{2, 3, 4\}$; learning rate $\in \{0.01, 0.03, 0.05\}$; l2 leaf reg $\in \{3, 5, 7, 10\}$	108
ANN (MLP)	hidden layer sizes $\in \{(32,16), (64,32), (32,)\}$; alpha $\in \{0.01, 0.1, 1.0\}$; learning rate init $\in \{0.001, 0.01\}$; early stopping (patience = 20)	18

Note. Inner-CV objective is AUROC across all algorithms. random state = 42. StandardScaler is applied to LR and ANN only (tree models are scale-invariant). Patience for early stopping in ANN = 20; validation fraction = 0.15. XGBoost subsample = 0.8 and colsample bytree = 0.8 are fixed (not searched). Following the Section 3.4 decision (C1), no SMOTE and no class weight options were applied in the main analysis.